

AN OVERVIEW OF AZERBAIJANI MEDIA WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF DEMOCRACY-BASED MEDIA THEORIES

Najafli M.

Dr.

Faculty of Communication, Department of Journalism

Independent Researcher

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-1254-4969>

Abstract

Within the scope of this study, the media structure in Azerbaijan is examined through the lens of democracy-based media theories, and the historical and theoretical dimensions of the relationship between media and democracy are analyzed. The study focuses on the media's role in supporting core democratic values such as freedom, equality, and participation; evaluations are made from the perspectives of liberal-democratic, social responsibility, participatory, and radical democratic media theories.

The historical development of Azerbaijani media is addressed from a broad perspective, spanning from the 19th century to the present day, with a particular comparison between the Soviet era and the post-independence media structure. Although certain efforts toward pluralism in the media landscape have been observed in the post-independence period, the study emphasizes that a centralized governance approach and an inadequate legal framework are key factors limiting press freedom and pluralism. Despite the increase in private media organizations, financial dependencies and repressive regulations are identified as obstacles to the development of independent journalism. It has been found that censorship mechanisms are currently maintained through legal and administrative means, and critical journalists face economic and legal pressures.

In the framework of democracy-based media theories, the media conditions in Azerbaijan are evaluated, and the weaknesses of the current media structure are revealed in terms of key elements such as press freedom, the functioning of public discussion platforms, and pluralism. Through literature review and document analysis methods, the study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of media policies and practices in the context of democratic values.

Keywords: freedom of expression, media pluralism, press freedom, democratization, Azerbaijan.

The Mutual Interaction Between Democracy and Media: Historical Process, Core Values, and Theoretical Approaches

Democracy, in its etymological roots, derives from the Greek terms “demos” (the people) and “cratos/cratein” (to rule, to govern), signifying the rule of the people (Schmidt, 2002, p. 13; Miller, 1994, p. 163). The concept was first used by Herodotus in Ancient Greece around the 5th century BCE and was implemented in the form of direct democracy in Athens (Uygun, 2017, p. 9–10). However, this early form of democracy granted political participation rights only to a specific group of citizens, excluding women, slaves, and foreigners from the system (Güzel, 2018, p. 217).

By the Middle Ages, the idea of democracy had largely receded into the background, with the notion of sovereignty legitimized through religious institutions (Kelsen, 2007, p. 164). Within the feudal system, the people far removed from the “demos” status lived mainly as serfs and peasants bound to the land, deprived of the right to participate in political life (Gül, 2012, p. 88–89). As the feudal economy was predominantly based on land ownership and the lord-serf relationship, peasants remained under the social and economic control of feudal lords (Huberman, 1974, p. 10).

Following the Crusades, the development of international trade and the growth of cities paved the way for the dissolution of the feudal structure. The increased mobility of serfs and their migration to commercial centers led to profound social transformations (Gül, 2012, p. 88–89). These changes laid the groundwork for the reconsideration of the concepts of people, state,

and rights in subsequent periods such as the Renaissance and the Enlightenment (Demir, 2013, p. 31). During the Renaissance and Enlightenment, the sanctity of political power was questioned, and new intellectual movements emerged in opposition to the authority of the Church and absolute monarchies.

In this context, the Magna Carta Libertatum, signed in 1215, stands out as the first constitutional document aimed at limiting the absolute sovereignty of the king (Dereköy, 2018, p. 158–159). The Glorious Revolution of 1688 in England marked the beginning of a new era in which the bourgeoisie assumed an active role in political life and served as a significant example for subsequent revolutions (Touraine, 2011, p. 272).

The French Revolution of 1789 strongly embedded the idea of democracy into political terminology and contributed to the broader adoption of popular sovereignty (Mankan, 2020, p. 124). Although the powers of the monarchy were limited through constitutional arrangements following the revolution, interruptions occurred with Napoleon's rise to power. Nevertheless, the revolution represented a critical stage in the formation of the fundamental principles and institutions of modern democracy. Around the same period, in the United States, the Declaration of Independence in 1776 and the adoption of the U.S. Constitution in 1788 institutionalized the principle of popular sovereignty, making significant contributions to the development of modern democracy (Keleş, 2012, p. 33).

The 19th century, shaped by the societal and economic transformations of the Industrial Revolution, be-

came a decisive period for the advancement of democracy. The intensification of labor class demands for rights and increasing calls for political participation amplified the discourse of freedom and equality during the 1848 Revolutions in Europe. In England, the Reform Act of 1832 expanded the electorate, laying the groundwork for a more inclusive parliamentary system (Keleş, 2012, p. 45). In the United States, the struggle to abolish slavery deepened the relationship between democracy and human rights, culminating in a major achievement with the ratification of the 13th Amendment in 1865 (Mankan, 2020, p. 137). The rise of nationalist movements and the emergence of nation-states further accelerated the spread of governance models based on popular sovereignty. However, political participation of women and lower social classes remained restricted for a long time.

The 20th century emerged as a paradoxical era in which democracy both advanced and regressed. Although the number of parliamentary regimes increased after World War I, the Great Depression of 1929 created a fertile ground for the rise of authoritarian regimes. Following World War II, however, the weakening of colonialism and the emergence of newly independent states accelerated the shift toward democratic forms of governance (Haytoğlu, 1997, p. 50). In addition, democratic systems were restructured in countries defeated in the war, such as Germany and Japan.

Today, democracy continues to exist as one of the fundamental political systems globally recognized for enabling public participation in governance. Having undergone various phases throughout history, democracy is now regarded as an indispensable component of social and political stability in the modern world.

Democracy stands out as a multilayered system of governance that is addressed both in its ideal and practical dimensions throughout history (Sartori, 1993, p. 9). On the one hand, the “actual” state—that is, democratic practices experienced in the social and political realms—and on the other hand, the “aspired” state—normative goals based on universal values such as freedom and equality—appear as core dynamics shaping the development of democracy. In this context, the intellectual heritage of democracy deepens through participatory and representative mechanisms, while also becoming institutionally rooted through elements such as the rule of law and the strengthening of civil society (Demir, 2010, p. 599).

Freedom and equality are two critical values that form the backbone of democratic systems. Freedom is not merely defined as the liberty to do whatever one desires, but also as the ability to realize one’s potential without infringing upon the rights of others (Aktaş, 2015, p. 90–91; Demir, 2010, p. 601). Rights such as freedom of thought and expression, freedom of association, and freedom of the press are prerequisites for the healthy functioning of a democratic order. Equality, on the other hand, refers to the principle that every individual should enjoy the same dignity and rights within the legal and political system, without discrimination (Demir, 2010, p. 602). This principle is implemented through the recognition of equal treatment and opportunities for different identity and belief groups; thus,

the state acts not with the aim of absolute uniformity among its citizens, but with the responsibility to protect them against discrimination (Görücü, 2019, p. 35–37).

Political representation plays a decisive role in the functioning of democracy. Elected officials who represent different segments of society under the roof of the parliament reflect the will of the people and formulate and implement public policies accordingly (Gözler, 2001, p. 117). In representative democracy, elections are the most important mechanism that materializes the principle of popular sovereignty, as the periodic act of voting reinforces both the accountability of political elites and the legitimacy of the system (Yüksel, 2017, p. 86–87). Moreover, the principle of participation is another essential element that ensures the continuity of democracy. Participation is strengthened not only through elections but also through tools of direct democracy such as referendums and popular vetoes, along with the active involvement of civil society organizations and professional associations (Aktan, 1997, p. 72; Demir, 2010, p. 603).

The sustainability of democratic order is closely tied to the existence of institutions based on the rule of law. The acceptance of legal norms as common rules binding both the state and society prevents arbitrary practices and serves to protect rights and freedoms (Erdoğan, 2020, p. 36). In this context, judicial independence and the right to a fair trial are among the fundamental guarantees of a democratic society (Chevalier, 2010, p. 92). Furthermore, the notion that sovereignty belongs to the people reflects the historical transformation from monarchical systems to nation-state structures (Gülsoy, 2016, p. 73; Sartori, 2014, p. 18). With this transformation, the legitimacy of political power began to derive from the citizens themselves, thereby strengthening the societal foundations of democratic regimes.

The development of civil society and the widespread participation in political life play an indispensable role in deepening the culture of democracy. Civil society serves as an institutional mechanism for carrying social demands into the public sphere and exercising the right to oversee and criticize the state (Çaha, 2005, p. 688). In this way, individuals are not limited to participating in democracy only through the ballot box; they also influence political decision-making processes through channels such as protests, petition campaigns, and voluntary organizations (Özbudun, 1975, p. 1; Çukurçayır, 2012). From this perspective, democracy is a dynamic model of governance that internalizes freedom and equality as complementary values, institutionalizes itself through the rule of law, and maintains interaction with society by keeping participation channels open.

As a political system based on the will of the people, democracy encompasses various institutions and processes. The healthy functioning of these institutions and processes depends on the presence of informed and critically thinking individuals. The accurate, impartial, and multifaceted flow of information that such individuals require is largely provided by the media (Kaya, 2001, p. 63). In democratic societies, the media plays a crucial role by enabling voters to make informed

choices, establishing an effective public oversight mechanism over political actors, and facilitating the discussion of social issues among the wider public (Curran & Seaton, 1992, p. 278).

In this context, the media is referred to as the "fourth estate" due to its role in monitoring the legislative, executive, and judicial branches on behalf of the public. The timely and accurate collection and dissemination of news that serves the public interest directly contributes to the formation of a free and healthy public sphere (Tartanoğlu, 2020, p. 68). In this regard, Dahl (1989), in his work *Polyarchy*, lists "access to alternative sources of information" among the eight institutional guarantees necessary for the functioning of a democratic system, emphasizing that a pluralistic media structure is essential for democracy. Similarly, Lijphart (1999) highlights that for a pluralist model of democracy to be realized, the media must reflect diverse viewpoints, and he warns that media monopolization poses a threat to media diversity.

The media is not limited to merely transmitting information and news; it also provides frameworks for how news and events are to be perceived. This function is highly influential in shaping public opinion. The content presented by mass communication tools may conflict with individuals' personal experiences, and more often, it transcends and shapes these experiences by creating a perception of reality (Kaya, 2001, p. 63). Therefore, the media largely determines how events and phenomena that the public cannot directly observe or analyze in depth are interpreted. In this regard, journalists occupy a strategic position in ensuring the public is accurately informed and in fostering critical thinking.

Fiss emphasizes that freedom of expression and freedom of the press are fundamental elements of democratic systems, arguing that without these freedoms, it is not possible to speak of genuine democracy. Freedom of expression enables citizens to access diverse opinions and information while making decisions about their own futures. Likewise, the media, as an indispensable tool of democratic participation, facilitates the circulation of political discourse and serves as a platform for dialogue among political actors (Işık, 2005, p. 117). At this point, ensuring a pluralistic media structure depends on the equal representation of different social groups and political tendencies. Especially during election periods, one of the media's most important responsibilities is to provide equal and fair coverage of political parties and candidates.

However, in practice, media organizations are often vulnerable to various economic, political, or ideological influences, which can lead to deviations from the principles of equality in representation and impartiality. Limited media visibility for smaller parties or excessive airtime allocated to ruling parties can result in voters receiving insufficient information about alternative policies (Lijphart, 1999, p. 12). Similarly, when media outlets are closely linked to executive power, they may fail to fulfill their watchdog role and instead merely reproduce the narratives of those in power. This leads to the narrowing of the pluralistic space for public debate, which is essential to sustaining a democratic society (Curran & Seaton, 1992, p. 278).

In democracies, the media should act in accordance with the principles of impartial and independent journalism, assuming the responsibility of "informing" and "enlightening" rather than "mobilizing supporters." The ideal function of the media is to provide platforms where diverse views and groups can express themselves, and to adhere as closely as possible to the principles of objectivity and transparency when framing events. For this to be realized, legal regulations must guarantee press freedom, journalists must remain committed to professional ethical standards, and measures must be taken to prevent media ownership from being concentrated under the control of a few actors.

Indeed, the relationship between media and democracy is shaped around two mutually reinforcing concepts. Democracy requires a neutral, diverse, and free media in order to realize values such as elections, participation, pluralism, and freedom (Tartanoğlu, 2020, p. 68). In turn, the media needs a democratic political framework and the rule of law in order to function effectively. Thus, while the media serves to raise political awareness among citizens, provide the public with unbiased information, and monitor those in power, it is also an indispensable instrument for ensuring the continuity and effectiveness of democracy. The mutual interdependence of these two elements stands out as one of the primary conditions for strengthening democratic systems.

In this context, democracy-based media theories examine the role of mass communication tools within democratic processes from various perspectives and expand the scope of their responsibilities toward society. In general, these theories envision that the media should function in ways that support democratic values such as freedom, equality, and participation. The fact that media structures change depending on the economic and political conditions of different periods explains why these theories, despite sharing similar concerns at their core, also exhibit important differences.

The liberal-democratic media theory is rooted in the Enlightenment concepts of the individual and freedom. Starting in the 17th century, the liberal approach emerged as a critique of the dogmatic elements of medieval Christian philosophy, emphasizing human reason and critical thinking (Adorno & Horkheimer, 2014). This approach advocates for the media to operate free from state intervention, based on private ownership, and to function as a monitor of governmental authority. In this model, the media's role as a "public watchdog" is essential. The liberal-democratic theory centers on the pursuit of truth by the press and conceptualizes the media as a mechanism that prevents the excessive use of state power. However, it has been criticized for its inability to address issues such as monopolization and commercialization that have emerged in the modern era (Laçiner, 2015).

Criticism stemming from the liberal approach and the increasingly apparent media monopolization of the 20th century laid the foundation for the social responsibility theory. Particularly within the context of a commercialized media environment, the observed decline of the "public service broadcasting" ideal brought the

issue of the media's ethical responsibilities to the forefront (Özgen, 1998). This theory argues that, in addition to press freedom, the media must ensure accurate public information and address social issues through a responsible broadcasting approach. The Hutchins Commission Report (1947) and Kent Cooper's concept of "the public's right to know" form the backbone of the social responsibility paradigm. What matters here is the idea that the media should not be reduced to an "unregulated playground of the free market," and that interventions aimed at serving the public good are deemed necessary (Laçiner, 2015, p. 30–31).

The participatory democratic media theory, which advocates for a more inclusive and locally responsive media, appears to be an extension of the liberal approach but actually emerges as a reaction to growing capital concentration and bureaucratic centralization (McQuail, 1994). According to this theory, the media should expand the public sphere and amplify the voices of various ethnic, cultural, and social groups. In particular, enabling minority and disadvantaged groups to own their own media outlets facilitates their transition from being merely the "governed" to becoming active participants in decision-making processes. Therefore, the participatory approach emphasizes being a "co-producer of news" rather than a mere "consumer of news." In this regard, the media should not be solely under the control of professional journalists and large capital interests; it must also include local, small-scale initiatives that allow for interactive and multidimensional participation (Yılmaz, 2011, p. 99).

Democratic media theory is essentially evaluated through the functions it provides to society. The *Many Voices, One World* report, also known as the "MacBride Report" published by UNESCO, details various media responsibilities such as providing information, enhancing social participation, motivating citizens, serving as a platform for public debate, and contributing to education and cultural development (Türkmen, 2011, p. 44). According to Raymond Williams, the media, when structured as a "public service," becomes one of the fundamental tools of social dialogue and democratic participation. Therefore, democratic media theory advocates for the existence of intermediary institutions to avoid unilateral state pressure and the dominance of private capital solely driven by profit motives (Yakışır, 2009, p. 37). The ultimate goal is to establish a media environment where diverse views can be freely expressed and which serves the ideal of participatory democracy.

The radical democratic media theory was shaped by James Curran's critiques, which highlight the shortcomings of the liberal media order (İrvan, 1994, p. 224–225). This theory advocates for the adoption of regulations that actively ensure pluralism, rather than normalizing monopolization within competitive media markets. Large media conglomerates formed through capital concentration tend to produce content within a narrow ideological framework, potentially restricting the expression of diverse social actors. In contrast, radical democratic media theory aims to overcome this limitation by encouraging "social opposition" to establish its own communication networks, thereby creating

alternative platforms outside the dominant media and preserving diversity. This approach envisions the development of media initiatives that can serve as voices of social dissent and the strengthening of networks capable of contributing to international solidarity.

All of these theories offer different perspectives on how the media should be positioned within the framework of democratic values. While liberal and social responsibility theories focus on press freedom and the public interest as safeguards against state oppression and market manipulation, participatory, democratic, and radical democratic approaches emphasize pluralism, local participation, and alternative media initiatives. The common ground among them is the recognition that the media is not merely a "channel of communication," but also a foundational pillar that builds and sustains the democratic order. Therefore, regardless of the theoretical framework it adopts, it is of critical importance for both democracy and freedom of thought that the media upholds the principles of social responsibility and democratic participation.

The Historical Development of Azerbaijani Media

The foundations of Azerbaijani media history were laid in the last quarter of the 19th century through bold initiatives undertaken under the strict censorship and bureaucratic obstacles of Tsarist Russia. During this period, the first example of the Azerbaijani press, the newspaper *Ekinchi*, began publication on July 22, 1875, through the efforts of Hasan Bey Zardabi (Orucov, 2006, p. 77). Among its primary goals were educating Azerbaijani society and fostering national consciousness. However, *Ekinchi* was forced to cease publication after 56 issues, on September 26, 1877 (Bayramoğlu, 1997, p. 38). The strong censorship mechanisms of the Tsarist regime and financial hardships posed constant barriers to national press initiatives like *Ekinchi*.

Following the closure of *Ekinchi*, *Ziya* became the first newspaper published in the Azerbaijani language in 1879, but it had to shut down in 1885 due to financial difficulties. At that time, the lack of printing equipment and the heavy conditions imposed by state control significantly restricted efforts to publish periodicals in the Azerbaijani language. Indeed, the magazine *Kashkul*, launched on January 1, 1883, faced similar challenges and ceased publication in 1891 after issuing 123 editions (Pirizade, 2019, p. 36).

The intensified censorship practices under the "General Regulations on Censorship" (1865), enacted by Tsarist Russia, placed severe limitations on press freedom in an environment where Azerbaijani national consciousness was beginning to emerge. Despite these harsh conditions, the press played a crucial role in societal modernization and identity formation (Aşırılı, 2023, pp. 16–20). Nevertheless, launching another Azerbaijani-language newspaper after the closure of *Kashkul* proved difficult. Finally, in 1903, the newspaper *Sharqi-Rus*, led by Muhammad Agha Shahtakhtinski, began publication. Although it lasted only two years (Quliyev, 2020, p. 9), *Sharqi-Rus* is remembered as a major milestone in the dissemination of

enlightenment ideas and the modernization process of Azerbaijani society.

At the beginning of the 20th century, the rise of liberal tendencies across Russia also found resonance in the Azerbaijani media landscape. Encouraged by this favorable atmosphere, efforts intensified in 1906 to obtain a publishing license for *Molla Nasreddin*, a magazine that would hold a distinguished place in the history of the Azerbaijani press. Led by Jalil Mammadguluzadeh, *Molla Nasreddin* published its first issue on April 7, 1906, focusing on the fight against societal ignorance, illiteracy, and backwardness. The magazine adopted a critical stance on political and social issues, using satire and humor to reach a broad readership. It provided a platform for diverse viewpoints during a time of intense ideological struggle. Despite interruptions, the magazine continued its publication until 1931 and became a unique and enduring voice in Azerbaijani media.

During the same period, newspapers such as *Hayat* and *Irshad* played significant roles in the spread of national ideology and Turkism in Azerbaijan, thereby contributing to the construction of national identity (Aşırılı, 2023, p. 62–67). These publications encouraged modernization and identity formation within society, bringing new perspectives to intellectual discourse and press culture. In summary, from the late 19th century to the first quarter of the 20th century, despite various external challenges, the Azerbaijani press evolved into an important platform reflecting society's aspirations for education, national consciousness, and modernization.

The transformation of Azerbaijani media beginning in the early 20th century took place in the shadow of major historical turning points, such as the collapse of the Russian Empire and the Bolshevik Revolution of 1917. In this context, the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic (ADR), declared shortly after the dissolution of the Transcaucasian Democratic Federative Republic on May 28, 1918, entered history as the first democratic and secular republic among Muslim-majority countries. With the establishment of the ADR, significant legal reforms were enacted in the field of press and journalism, laying the groundwork for strengthening freedom of expression.

One of the most noteworthy steps taken during this period was the adoption of the *Press Statute* by the Parliament of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic (ADR) on October 30, 1919. This legislation provided the first comprehensive legal framework regulating press activities in Azerbaijan and facilitated the institutionalization of initiatives in the printing and publishing sectors. Aimed at protecting press freedom and the rights of journalists, the regulation also included provisions to minimize government interference. Notably, while only about 40 newspapers had been published in the Azerbaijani language prior to May 1918, this number exceeded 200 during the ADR's 23-month tenure (Aşırılı, 2023, p. 299). The newspaper *Azerbaijan* which began publication during this period, stood out as one of the most important publications reflecting the ideals of the republic and its commitment to press freedom (Yaqublu, 1999).

The year 1920, which marked the formal establishment of Soviet rule in Azerbaijan, became a turning point in the country's political and social structure, placing media institutions squarely at the center of ideological control. Bolshevik leaders restructured the Azerbaijani press under strict state supervision, transforming it into one of the primary propaganda tools of socialist ideology (Pirizade, 2019, p. 84). Under Stalin's rule, beginning in 1924, the rigid implementation of collectivization policies increased pressure on the intellectual community, leading to the persecution of numerous journalists and writers (Pirizade, 2019, p. 100). During this period, newspapers such as *Azerbaijani Kommunist*, *Bakinskiy Rabochiy*, and *Komsomolskaya Pravda* played a central role in legitimizing party politics through their alignment with the Communist Party's ideological line.

Over the more than 70 years of Soviet dominance, journalism in Azerbaijan became increasingly professionalized, journalism education gained prominence in universities, and the technical infrastructure of the media developed. However, these advancements largely served to reinforce a monolithic media environment that catered to the interests of the Communist Party. At the same time, the establishment of official Soviet newspapers and the publication of approximately 40 regional newspapers (Temir, 2021, p. 162) enabled the dissemination of the state's dominant ideology across various geographical areas.

Radio and television broadcasting were also utilized as tools of ideological control by the state throughout the Soviet period. Although the first radio experiments in Azerbaijan were conducted in Ganja during the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic era, official records mark the beginning of radio broadcasting as November 6, 1926 (Temir, 2021, p. 162). Television broadcasting began after the launch of central broadcasts in Moscow in 1931, with the foundation of the Baku Television Studio in 1954 and its transition to regular broadcasting on February 14, 1956 (Alizade & Muharremli, 2006, p. 139).

By the late 1980s, the economic crisis within the Soviet Union, internal divisions within the Communist Party, and the eruption of the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict paved the way for the rise of the freedom movement in Azerbaijan and a gradual weakening of Soviet ideology (Genberli, 2001, p. 199). Particularly, Mikhail Gorbachev's *perestroika* and *glasnost* policies allowed Azerbaijani media to evolve toward a more independent path, fostering pluralism. As a result, in the post-Soviet period, the media began to operate in a freer environment, transforming into a structure that more actively represented the views and demands of different segments of society. This transformation contributed to the amplification of diverse voices in Azerbaijani society and a relative expansion of press freedom and freedom of expression.

The late 1980s, marking the beginning of the Soviet Union's collapse, was also a period in which national consciousness in Azerbaijan reawakened and demands for democratization accelerated. During this time, the relative openness provided by the *perestroika*

and *glasnost* policies enabled the emergence of independent media outlets. One notable development was the publication of the first issue of the newspaper *Azerbaijan* on October 6, 1989, under the editorial leadership of Sabir Rustamkhanli and Sharif Karimli, symbolizing the revival of independent journalism. In the same period, newspapers such as *Sahar* and *Azadliq* reinforced the media's role in voicing the growing demand for freedom in Azerbaijan. The activities carried out under the umbrella of the Azerbaijan Popular Front Party (APFP) and its official publication *Azadliq* played a key role in promoting the idea of independence and mobilizing the masses (Selimov, 1999, p. 9). Launched at the end of 1989, *Azadliq*, meaning "freedom," not only emphasized the concept in its name but also inspired many media outlets that would be established in the following years.

In the 1990s, coinciding with the collapse of the Soviet Union, various newspaper initiatives were launched in Azerbaijan, and journalistic activities gained significant momentum. During this period, a range of publications emerged, including *Zerkalo* and *Ses* (1990), *Yeni Musavat*, *İki Sahil*, *525-ci qezet*, and *Yeni Azerbaijan* (1991–1992) (Temir, 2021, p. 169). While some of these newspapers functioned as official organs of the state or political parties, others positioned themselves as independent media outlets. This diversity revealed three main structures shaped by ideological orientations and financial resources: state-supported media, party-affiliated media, and independent media initiatives. For instance, *525-ci qezet* and *Şark*, established in the 1990s, are considered typical examples of independent media, whereas *Yeni Azerbaijan*, which became the official publication of the New Azerbaijan Party (YAP) founded by Heydar Aliyev in 1993, served as a platform for conveying the party's agenda to the public.

Following Azerbaijan's official declaration of independence on October 18, 1991, the expectation for media pluralism became increasingly pronounced. Journalists whose areas of operation had been limited during the Soviet period now sought to assume a more active role in shaping public opinion within a broader framework of freedom. Accordingly, the media not only fulfilled a news transmission function but also played a critical role in organizing social opposition and fostering a culture of democratic participation. In the early years of independence, the media landscape became a space for ideological and political diversity, forming a new framework in which state, party, and independent entities coexisted. In the years that followed, steps toward institutionalization and professionalization were built upon this foundation.

On the other hand, the transformation in Azerbaijan's media environment also extended to the television and radio sectors. *Azerbaijan State Television and Radio* (AzTV), established in 1956 and the sole official broadcasting body during the Soviet period, operated without competition for a long time (İsgenderli, 2007, p. 59). However, with the dissolution of the Soviet Union, private television and radio channels began to proliferate rapidly during the so-called "transition period." Within this context, a channel known as *BMTI*, which

began broadcasting in 1993, marked one of the first steps toward private broadcasting, despite its brief lifespan. Additionally, *ANS Press*, founded in 1991 as a news agency, initially produced a single program titled "Haberci" but gradually evolved into a comprehensive television channel (Temir, 2021, p. 169). ANS played a pivotal role in strengthening the legitimacy of private media in the public eye with its innovative broadcast formats. Due to the absence of formal legal regulations during this period, private television and radio broadcasting largely operated based on the discretion of media executives until 2002 (Bağırzade, 2018, p. 63).

Significant steps toward freedom of expression and press freedom in Azerbaijan gained momentum with the adoption of the country's first national Constitution in 1995. Article 47 of the Constitution guarantees "freedom of thought and speech," while Article 50 ensures "freedom of information," thus forming the legal foundation for press and broadcasting activities (Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 1995). Subsequently, the decree signed by President Heydar Aliyev in 1998 titled "Additional Measures to Ensure Freedom of Expression, Thought, and Information in the Republic of Azerbaijan" officially abolished censorship.

From the second half of the 1990s onward, new television broadcasters began to emerge. *Space TV* started operations in 1997, followed by *Lider TV* in 2000 and *ATV (Azad Azerbaijan Television)* in 2002. A similar surge was observed in the radio sector. *ANS ÇM* (named after Chingiz Mustafayev), which began broadcasting in 1994, became one of the country's first private radio stations (Memmedov, 2007, p. 22). With the use of the FM band starting in 1997, several radio channels launched, including *Azad Azerbaijan Radio (106.3 FM)*, *Anten Radio (101 FM)*, *Burç FM (100.5 FM)*, and *Lider Radio (107 FM)* (Rüstəmov, 2011, p. 60). As a result, the state monopoly that had characterized broadcasting during the Soviet era gave way to a more pluralistic and dynamic media environment in the late 1990s and early 2000s.

The use of new media tools in Azerbaijan also developed gradually beginning in the 1990s and gained notable momentum after 1997. A key milestone in the country's digital journey was achieved in 1991 when the Institute of Information Technologies of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences established the first internet connection. In 1995, the launch of the website www.ab.az under the Academy accelerated practical use of the internet. This was followed by the launch of www.science.gov.az on September 26, 2001, by decision of the Academy's Presidium, which helped bring the research community into the online space.

In the field of journalism, *Yeni Musavat* (www.musavat.com) and the Russian-language *Zerkalo* (www.zerkalo.az) became some of the first outlets to establish an online presence. Subsequently, online versions of print media such as *Turan News Agency* (www.turaninfo.com), *Azadliq* (www.azadliq.az), *525-ci qezet* (www.525ci.com), and *Ayna* (www.ayna.com) were also launched (Xalidoğlu, 2016, p. 25). Although traditional media initially hesi-

tated to engage with digital platforms, the decline in internet access costs and improvements in infrastructure accelerated the transition to online journalism. At a time when email communication was becoming widespread and social media had not yet emerged, the accessibility of web-based news contributed significantly to public interest in online media platforms in Azerbaijan.

In the post-independence period, a series of legal and institutional reforms were implemented in Azerbaijan's media sector. Following the abolition of censorship, the Law on Mass Media came into force in 1999, comprehensively defining the scope of activities for media outlets (Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on Mass Media, 1999). It was noted that the law was drafted by examining the legal frameworks of countries such as the United States, Canada, Russia, Austria, and Turkey, and by taking international standards into account. Subsequently, amendments made in 2001 and 2002 abolished Article 5, which pertained to radio and television broadcasting, and this field was later regulated under a separate law—*The Law on Television and Radio Broadcasting*—adopted on June 25, 2002 (Esenov, 2013, p. 76).

The search for institutionalization in the media sector also led to changes in ministerial and administrative structures. In 2001, the Ministry of Press and Information was dissolved (Presidential Decree on the Dissolution of the Ministry of Press and Information of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2001), and governance of the sector was continued through other institutions. Within this context, the First Congress of Azerbaijani Journalists, held on March 15, 2003, established the Azerbaijani Press Council with the aim of regulating the relationship between the media, the government, and society (Bakı Xəbər, 2012). Later, on July 31, 2008, President İlham Aliyev signed a decree approving the establishment of the *State Support Fund for the Development of Mass Media in the Republic of Azerbaijan* (Presidential Decree on the Establishment of the State Support Fund, 2008). Following this, the Fund, officially launched on May 22, 2009, began providing financial and institutional support to media organizations.

Media-related reforms continued into the new period. The *Media Development Agency*, established by Presidential Decree on January 12, 2021, initiated various projects to support the institutional development and financial independence of print and digital media (Charter of the Media Development Agency of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2021). A new law entitled *On Media*, which entered into force on December 30, 2021, introduced changes in the regulatory structure for radio and television broadcasting. It abolished the National Television and Radio Council (NTRC) and replaced it with a new body called the *Audiovisual Council* (Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on Media, 2021).

Additionally, this law introduced the *Media Registry* system, aimed at officially registering media professionals and ensuring their compliance with certain legal standards. While this model was defended on the grounds that it would help protect the official rights of

journalists, it also drew criticism for potentially restricting media freedom. The registry is designed to strengthen regulatory oversight over unregistered media activity, which has raised concerns among critics about its implications for press independence.

Media Dynamics in Azerbaijan: Press Freedom, Censorship, and the Pursuit of Democratization

The roots of media transformations in Azerbaijan stem from efforts to break away from the Soviet legacy and the desire to establish an independent press structure in the early 1990s. However, since 1993, a centralized approach to governance has increasingly strengthened the state's influence over the media due to weak institutional capacity and an inadequate legal framework to sufficiently protect media freedom (Mirakif, 2024). Most television channels and radio stations are directly or indirectly controlled by state institutions or individuals close to the ruling power. Official broadcasters have largely assumed the mission of legitimizing government policies and consolidating public opinion around them. In contrast, media outlets that attempt to operate independently or critically face administrative, financial, and legal pressures that often force them to cease operations (HRW, 2024; Ələsgərli, 2022).

The institutional structure of media organizations in Azerbaijan is predominantly concentrated in the hands of pro-government capital. Newspaper circulation has declined significantly, and a one-dimensional broadcasting trend dominates the television landscape. Public broadcasters, instead of adopting independent editorial policies, tend to reproduce official discourse. In the private sector, the close ties between media owners and the government lead to editorial lines that align closely with government perspectives (RSF, 2021).

The institutionalization and quality of journalism as a profession require strong educational institutions. However, the closure of journalism faculties in several private universities in Azerbaijan has limited the potential for developing a skilled media workforce (Salamov, 2020, p. 584). In the remaining state universities, journalism education is largely theoretical, with insufficient emphasis on practical training and independent reporting. This situation hampers the development of professional standards and contributes to the decline of competition and pluralism in the media sector.

The economic dependence of media outlets on state subsidies or advertising revenues from business circles close to the government eliminates financial autonomy. This lack of autonomy not only hinders the ability of media organizations to adopt a critical editorial stance but also reinforces a “single-voice” media environment (RSF, 2021). A large portion of advertising and sponsorship revenues is directed toward government-controlled channels or newspapers, making economic sustainability virtually impossible for opposition or independent media outlets.

In the post-independence period, various laws and regulations have been enacted to govern the media landscape in Azerbaijan; however, these legal frameworks have largely included provisions that protect state interests while restricting freedom of expression.

Particularly since 2014, new regulations have mandated that media outlets be registered in a state-run system, required journalists to hold an “official press card” to practice their profession, and subjected news content to strict oversight (RSF, 2023).

The reimplementing of creativity exams after 2014, in theory, aimed to assess relevant journalistic skills and introduce more qualified individuals to the profession (Nuriyev, 2021). In practice, however, these exams have been criticized for allegedly filtering candidates based on their political views or perceived loyalty to the ruling authorities. As a result, state control and approval mechanisms over entry into journalism have been further strengthened, weakening the presence of critical voices in the media (Qocayev, 2017).

The new media law that came into force in February 2022 subjects Azerbaijani journalists to a state-supervised registration system and allows news content to be banned on the grounds of disseminating “false information” (RSF, 2023). This regulation has been interpreted not as a measure to protect press freedom, but rather as a legal framework designed to suppress content that might provoke public dissatisfaction with the state. Lawsuits based on accusations of spreading false information place journalists and their sources under threat, thereby undermining the principle of source confidentiality.

Another dimension of the legal framework involves provisions that restrict the funding sources of independent media outlets. Limitations on accepting advertisements, sponsorships, or donations weaken the economic infrastructure of independent media and reinforce the monopoly of state-controlled outlets (FPU, n.d.). Through these mechanisms, media organizations are prohibited from accepting advertising or donations without state approval; consequently, those with cut-off financial channels are forced to cease operations.

In Azerbaijan, journalists, social media activists, and civil society representatives are systematically subjected to pressure, particularly for publications or posts that criticize the government. Arbitrary detention and arrest by security forces, judicial prosecutions, heavy fines, and passport restrictions are frequently employed to silence dissenting or independent voices (HRW, 2024).

Reports published by Reporters Without Borders (RSF) indicate that incidents of physical violence and threats against critical journalists have reached alarming levels, with perpetrators often going unpunished (RSF, 2024). This climate of impunity makes journalists increasingly vulnerable and creates a lack of deterrence that paves the way for further attacks.

The repressive environment and harsh enforcement mechanisms compel journalists and media outlets to resort to self-censorship. Reporters, newsrooms, and television channels often avoid covering critical stories in order to steer clear of potential backlash from the state and security forces (Kızılkın, 1988, p. 161). This situation hinders the public’s access to complete and impartial information and results in many societal issues remaining unseen. A particularly striking example occurred in September 2023, when the government im-

posed strict censorship during developments in the Nagorno-Karabakh region and barred critical journalists from reporting on the ground—an action that sparked international criticism (Jafarova & Erzurum, 2024, pp. 525–542).

Indeed, the current state of the media landscape in Azerbaijan reveals serious structural problems due to state control, financial pressures, legal restrictions, and sanctions imposed on journalists. When evaluated within the framework of democracy-based media theories:

- The liberal-democratic media theory, rooted in Enlightenment thought, emphasizes individual freedoms and limiting state intervention (Adorno & Horkheimer, 2014; Yıkışır, 2009). This approach highlights the role of the press as a “public watchdog,” advocating for media independence from the state and the prevention of excessive governmental power through private ownership.

In Azerbaijan, the fact that the majority of television, radio, and print media outlets are controlled by the state or pro-government capital groups significantly undermines the editorial independence of media organizations (HRW, 2024; Ələsgərli, 2022). This reality clearly contradicts the liberal-democratic theory’s premise that the media should remain autonomous from the state. As a result, media, which is expected to serve as a public watchdog, has instead become a tool of state propaganda in Azerbaijan.

One of the main criticisms of the liberal theory is its inadequacy in addressing modern issues of monopolization and commercialization (Laçiner, 2015). In the Azerbaijani context, the monopolization problem is manifested in the state-led or pro-government capital’s domination of the media sector. The concentration of advertising and financial resources in the hands of government-aligned entities further reduces the chances of survival for opposition media, effectively silencing alternative voices (RSF, 2021).

In this regard, from the perspective of liberal-democratic media theory, the media system in Azerbaijan largely contradicts the goals of “individual freedom” and “government oversight.” The absence of the necessary economic and legal conditions for sustaining opposition and independent journalism creates a reality far from meeting the theoretical expectations.

- The social responsibility theory emphasizes the necessity of advocating for the public good in an increasingly commercialized media environment. Its aim is not only to safeguard press freedom but also to uphold ethical journalism principles and prioritize societal benefit (Özgen, 1998; Yılmaz, 2011). In this context, the Hutchins Commission Report (1947) and Kent Cooper’s concept of “the public’s right to know” underscore the media’s duty to act in the interest of society (Laçiner, 2015).

In Azerbaijan, the fact that broadcasting policies are predominantly shaped around the political and ideological interests of the ruling power weakens the principle of “broadcasting for the public good.” The government’s systematic suppression of critical journalists and civil society actors through methods such as arbitrary detentions, arrests, and prosecutions (HRW,

2024) significantly hinders journalism based on public interest.

Social responsibility theory advocates for a media structure capable of self-regulation and accountability to the public. However, in Azerbaijan, legal and financial restrictions on media organizations—such as state control over advertising revenues and the mandatory “official press card”—eliminate the possibility of self-regulation and reinforce governmental oversight. As a result, instead of allowing for diverse perspectives on socio-political issues, the media is compelled to align with the government narrative.

The current conditions in Azerbaijan demonstrate that the principles advocated by social responsibility theory—such as public interest, ethical broadcasting, and serving the welfare of society—have also been largely undermined. The media operates with a policy that centers on the interests of the ruling power, severely damaging the public’s right to access accurate, impartial, and critical information.

- Participatory democratic media theory promotes a grassroots-oriented media model that is rooted in local dynamics and diverse social groups. According to McQuail (1994), this theory emerged as a response to the growing concentration of capital and bureaucratic centralization, aiming to amplify the voices of various communities and enable the public to take an active role in media production processes.

In Azerbaijan, the media landscape is largely monopolized by state-led or pro-government institutions. The space for minority groups, opposition parties, civil society formations, and local initiatives to establish their own distinct media outlets has steadily diminished. Harsh censorship policies and threats of closure or legal action against independent platforms have made it extremely difficult for alternative, grassroots media to flourish (RSF, 2022; Jafarova & Erzurum, 2024).

Participatory democratic theory envisions a media system where news production is not confined to professional journalists and major capital holders, but includes channels that allow public engagement in content creation (Yılmaz, 2011). However, in Azerbaijan, the intense pressure on media organizations and the systematic prosecution of social media activists (HRW, 2024) hinder the sustainability of local and small-scale media ventures. As a result, the transition of citizens from mere “consumers” to active “participants” in news and content production is severely limited.

All of these conditions greatly obstruct the realization of participatory democratic media theory in Azerbaijan. The potential for civic engagement and the amplification of local voices is either suppressed or remains highly restricted due to repressive policies and financial dependency.

- Radical democratic media theory is based on James Curran’s critiques of the shortcomings of the liberal order. Rather than accepting monopolization as a natural outcome, this theory advocates for legal regulations that ensure true pluralism and supports the establishment of independent communication networks by social opposition groups (İrvan, 1994).

In Azerbaijan, capital concentration in the media sector often manifests as monopolization by state-supported or pro-government business elites. Radical democratic theory argues that in order to break such concentration, social opposition must be able to establish its own communication channels. However, the political climate in Azerbaijan imposes strict measures against the creation of such alternative platforms. Due to legal and financial pressures, the sustainability of opposition or independent publications is extremely difficult (Qocayev, 2017).

The radical democratic approach also emphasizes the role of not only national actors, but also the international community and civil society in contributing to democratic media structures. In Azerbaijan, although reports and warnings from international media organizations and human rights groups—such as RSF and HRW—occasionally gain attention, these efforts have yet to generate lasting change in the face of the government’s censorship and surveillance mechanisms.

As a result, the development of alternative platforms and the realization of genuine pluralism, as envisioned by radical democratic media theory, face serious obstacles in Azerbaijan. Efforts by opposition voices to build their own networks and to engage in international solidarity are heavily constrained by state repression (RSF, 2024).

This situation negatively affects Azerbaijan’s democratization process and its standards of freedom of expression. The implementation of fundamental principles emphasized by various media theories—such as freedom, participation, public debate, and pluralism—can only be realized through legal reforms that guarantee freedom of expression and a profound transformation of the government’s repressive stance. While international human rights organizations and press watchdogs (e.g., RSF, HRW) consistently emphasize the need for such a transformation through their reports, current conditions make it difficult for democratic values to take root within Azerbaijan’s media system. Therefore, strengthening local civil society and enhancing international solidarity are critically important for establishing a functioning democratic media environment in Azerbaijan.

The ability of individuals to form opinions freely depends primarily on their right to access accurate and unmanipulated information. The emergence of ideas relies on the free circulation and discussion of information, and any form of restriction or distortion of information indirectly hinders freedom of thought (Kızıllıkan, 1988, p. 161). In this context, the suppression of Azerbaijani media outlets and their adherence to a single-voiced editorial line limit the public’s access to diverse viewpoints, thereby weakening freedom of thought in practice. Consequently, the obstruction of information flow through censorship or similar means poses a threat not only to individuals but to the overall development of society.

Censorship has manifested in various forms throughout history—from state-imposed restrictions to societal pressure and self-censorship at the individual level (Kızıllıkan, 1988, p. 161). State-imposed censor-

ship is often justified under the pretexts of “national security” or “public order” (Çelik & Tonta, 1996, p. 4). In the case of Azerbaijan, these justifications have been incorporated into legal regulations and instrumentalized to restrict journalistic activities. However, international human rights organizations argue that such restrictions, imposed under the guise of “protecting the public interest,” actually undermine democratic rights (Çelik & Tonta, 1996, p. 4).

Freedom of thought and freedom of expression are recognized as inviolable rights in many international human rights treaties and constitutional frameworks (TÜGİK, p. 113; Hafizoğulları, p. 10). These rights safeguard both the physical and mental integrity of individuals and guarantee their ability to adopt any belief and express it freely (Erdem, p. 12). However, in Azerbaijan, the increasing mechanisms of control over press institutions restrict the applicability of these rights and hinder journalists and media organizations from operating freely. Freedom of thought—elevated in significance during the Enlightenment and considered one of the cornerstones of modern human rights theory (Erdem, p. 12)—cannot function as intended under such repressive conditions.

Freedom of expression, as the public manifestation of freedom of thought, refers to an individual's right to convey their ideas through various means and channels (Akgül, 2012, p. 3). Historically and philosophically, the foundations of this freedom can be traced back to John Milton's *Areopagitica*, where he emphasized “the freedom to argue, express, and know according to one's conscience” (Werhan, p. 3)—a concept regarded as one of the pillars of contemporary democracies. Thinkers such as Spinoza, Locke, and Mill also argued that a free and open debate environment is essential for the development of public reason (Ağaoğulları, Zabcı & Ergün, p. 62–71; Mill, 2012, p. 58). However, in Azerbaijan, censorship and self-censorship practices significantly undermine the free discussion space these philosophers envisioned.

Freedom of the press, as the institutional dimension of freedom of expression, plays a critical role in ensuring democratic functioning (Danışman, p. 2). Through an autonomous press, the public is accurately informed and authorities are held accountable. Thinkers like Jeremy Bentham described the press as the “watchdog” of society, demonstrating the historical roots of this vital role. In the case of Azerbaijan, however, the dominance of single-voiced broadcasting and repressive measures against journalists not only limit access to diverse information but also weaken the principles of democratic participation and transparency. Thus, restrictions on press freedom violate individual rights while also calling into question the legitimacy of political leaders and the future of society (Yazıcı, 2008, p. 35; Dönmezer, p. 44).

The disruption of the right to access information and the implementation of censorship in its various forms not only undermine individual knowledge but also restrict broader societal progress. As observed in the case of Azerbaijan, pressures on the media and uniformity in broadcasting indirectly weaken freedom of

thought and render press freedom—one of the essential pillars of democratic functioning—ineffective.

CONCLUSION

Azerbaijan's media system reflects the traces of a long historical trajectory that began with the rise of national consciousness in the late 19th century and evolved into a monolithic structure during the Soviet era. In the post-independence period, short-lived liberal openings were soon followed by a shift toward centralized control. As a result, fundamental principles critical to democracy—such as “freedom of expression,” “pluralism,” and “public interest”—have not been effectively implemented due to state-led broadcasting, financial constraints, and pressure on critical voices. Consequently, the core functions of journalism—monitoring public power and providing diverse information to society—have been significantly undermined.

Democracy-based media theories emphasize that the press should build a free and impartial public sphere. However, in the case of Azerbaijan, legal regulations are predominantly designed to serve political power, making it difficult for journalists to work independently and preventing civil society from effectively participating in public debate. This has led most media outlets to adopt a single narrative and has limited the public's access to diverse viewpoints.

To reverse this situation, a legal reform process must first be initiated based on the guarantees of an independent judiciary and the rule of law. Norms protecting freedom of expression and the press must go beyond mere legislative text and become genuinely effective in practice—thereby preventing arbitrary investigations and detentions. Financial autonomy is also a key component of this process: enabling media outlets to obtain advertising revenue or sponsorships under fair competition conditions, expanding access to alternative funding sources, and facilitating the survival of independent journalism initiatives.

In addition, the promotion of high-quality journalism education and professional ethics will help media professionals adhere to professional standards and cultivate a sense of public responsibility. Strengthening independent press organizations will foster solidarity among journalists and contribute to a more autonomous and pluralistic media environment. Enhancing civil society's influence over the media will not only support the production of critical content but also ensure that social issues are brought into the public spotlight. In this context, cooperation and knowledge exchange with international organizations can play a pivotal role in promoting universal norms and standards within the media sector.

Moreover, the opportunities offered by digitalization must be effectively utilized. Online journalism and social media platforms have the potential to bypass censorship and state control, becoming a voice for diverse segments of the population—particularly the youth. However, for this potential to be realized, it is essential to reconsider regulations and restrictions that limit internet freedom.

Overall, the establishment of a democratic media system is of key importance in enabling Azerbaijan's political and social structures to evolve toward a more

participatory and transparent framework. Reducing pressure on the media and implementing institutional reforms will strengthen freedom of expression and pluralism, thereby accelerating the country's democratization process. The eventual implementation of such reforms will not only guarantee journalists' rights but also ensure that the broader society enjoys access to information, freedom of expression, and participation in public decision-making-ultimately enhancing Azerbaijan's democratic visibility on the international stage.

References

1. Adorno, T., & Horkheimer, M. (2014). *Aydınlanmanın diyalektiği* (N. Ülner, Çev.). Kabalcı Yayıncılık.
2. Ağaoğulları, M. A., Çulfa Zabcı, F., & Ergün, R. (2005). *Kral-devletten ulus-devlete*. İmge Kitabevi.
3. Aktan, C. C. (1997). Siyasal ve sivil özgürlükler, demokrasi ve Türkiye. *Yeni Türkiye Dergisi*, 1(18), 72.
4. Aktaş, M. (2015). Demokrasi kavramına eleştirel bir bakış. *Muş Alparslan Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 1(3), 89–91.
5. Alizade, Y., & Muharremli, G. (2006). *Azerbaycan efiri (yayın), tarih ve çağdaşlık*. Nurlan Yayınları.
6. Aşırılı, A. (2023). *Azerbaycan medya tarihi*. Bakü.
7. Azerbaycan Respublikasının Konstitusiyası. (1995). <https://e-qanun.az/framework/897>
8. Azerbaycan Respublikasının Medianın İnkişafı Agentliyinin Nizamnaməsi. (2021). <https://president.az/az/articles/view/50115>
9. Azerbaycan Respublikasının Mətbuat və İnformasiya Nazirliyinin ləğv edilməsi haqqında Azerbaycan Respublikası Prezidentinin Fərmanı. (2001). <https://e-qanun.az/framework/2446>
10. Azerbaycan Respublikasının Prezidenti yanında Kütləvi İnformasiya Vasitələrinin İnkişafına Dövlət Dəstəyi Fondunun yaradılması haqqında Azerbaycan Respublikası Prezidentinin Fərmanı. (2008). https://e-qanun.az/framework/16497#_edn1
11. Bağırzadə, N. (2018). *Bağımsızlık sonrası Azerbaycan'da yazılı basının tarihsel gelişim süreci* [Yüksek lisans tezi]. Akdeniz Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
12. Bayramoğlu, A. (1997). *Şamahı'da maarif ve aydınlanma*. Maarif Yayınevi.
13. Chevallier, J. (2010). *Hukuk devleti* (E. C. Gürçan, Çev.). İmaj Yayınevi.
14. Curran, J., & Seaton, J. (1992). *Power without responsibility: The press and broadcasting in Britain*. Routledge.
15. Çaha, Ö. (2005). *Aşkın (transandantal) devletten sivil topluma*. İstanbul.
16. Çelik, A., & Tonta, Y. (Eds.). (1996). *Düşünce özgürlüğü, bilgi edinme özgürlüğü ve bilgi hizmetleri*. Türk Kütüphaneciler Derneği.
17. Çukurçayır, M. A. (2012). *Siyasal katılma ve yerel demokrasi*. Çizgi Kitabevi.
18. Danışman, A. (1982). *Basın özgürlüğünün sağlanması önlemleri: Devletin basın karşısındaki aktif tutumu*. Ankara Üniversitesi Yayın Yüksek Okulu Yayınları No. 1.
19. Demir, H. (2013). Demokrasi düşüncesinin gelişimi bağlamında demokrasi ve demokrasi karşıtı görüşler: Giovanni Sartori ve Carl Schmitt [Yüksek lisans tezi]. Hacettepe Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
20. Demir, N. (2010). Demokrasinin temel ilkeleri ve modern demokrasi kuramları. *Ege Akademik Bakış Dergisi*, 10(2), 597–611.
21. Dereköy, S. (2018). Magna Carta (Büyük Ferman) bir Magna Sancta (Büyük Kutsal) mı? *Uluslararası Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 11(56), 158–159.
22. Ələsgərli, N. (2022). Azerbaycanda jurnalistika təhsili sıfır səviyyəsindədir. <https://yenisabah.az/azerbaycanda-jurnalistika-tehsili-sifir-seviyyesindedir>
23. Ensarov, V. (2006). Sovyetler Birliği Dönemi'nde Azerbaycan'da görsel-işitsel yayıncılık ve habercilik anlayışı. *Atatürk İletişim Dergisi*, 1, 139.
24. Ensarov, V. (2013). Azerbaycan'da özel radyo ve televizyon yayıncılığı. *AJIT-e: Online Academic Journal of Information Technology*, 4(11), 71–90.
25. Erdem, F. H. (1988). Düşünce özgürlüğü ve demokrasi. *Ankara Barosu Dergisi*, 54(1).
26. Erdoğan, M. (2020). *Hukukun üstünlüğü elkitabı*. Özgürlük Araştırmaları Derneği.
27. Free Press Unlimited (FPU). (t.y.). *Azerbaijan*. <https://www.freepressunlimited.org/en/countries/azerbaijan>
28. Genberli, R. (2001). Azerbaycan'da bitmeyen geçiş süreci ve medya çıkmazı. *Avrasya Dosyası: Üç Aylık İlişkiler ve Stratejik Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 7(1), 197–220.
29. Görücü, V. (2019). *Türkiye'de katılımcı demokrasi* [Doktora tezi]. Kırıkkale Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
30. Gözler, K. (2001). *Anayasa hukukuna giriş: Genel esaslar ve Türk anayasa hukuku*. Ekin Kitabevi Yayınları.
31. Gül, M. (2012). *Orta Çağ Avrupa tarihi*. Bilge Kültür Sanat Yayıncılık.
32. Gülsoy, T. (2006). Milletin temsili. *Kamu Hukuku Arşivi*, 9(2), 71–86.
33. Güzel, M. N. (2018). Antik demokrasi ve modern demokrasi kavramlarının kuvvetler ayrılığı ilkesi çerçevesinde değerlendirilmesi. *Dicle Üniversitesi Hukuk Fakültesi Dergisi*, 38(23), 217.
34. Güzel, M. N. (2018). Antik demokrasi ve modern demokrasi kavramlarının kuvvetler ayrılığı ilkesi çerçevesinde değerlendirilmesi. *Dicle Üniversitesi Hukuk Fakültesi Dergisi*, 38(23), 217.
35. Hafizoğulları, Z. (1994). Liberal demokratik bir hukuk düzeninde ifade hürriyetinin sınırı. *İnsan Hakları Merkezi Dergisi*, 2(2).
36. Haytoğlu, E. (1997). Türkiye'de demokratikleşme süreci ve 1945'te çok partili siyasi hayata geçişin nedenleri (1908–1945). *Pamukkale Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 3(1), 50.
37. Huberman, L. (1974). *Feodal toplumdun yirminci yüzyıla* (M. Belge, Çev.). Bilim Yayınları.

38. Human Rights Watch (HRW). (2024). *World report 2024: Azerbaijan*. <https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2024/country-chapters/azerbaijan>
39. Işık, M. (2005). Medya ve demokrasi paradoksu: Medya yoluyla demokrasinin tehdit edilmesi. *Selçuk İletişim*, 3(4), 114–121.
40. İsgöndərli, S. (2007). Televizyon ve radyonun hukuki düzenlenmesi. *TV Plyus Dergisi*, (6).
41. Jafarova, K., & Erzurum, F. (2024). Modern Azərbaycan gazeteciliği: 1991'den günümüze. *TRT Akademi*, 9(21), 514–531.
42. John, K. (2010). *Medya ve demokrasi* (H. Şahin, Çev., 4. bs.). Ayrıntı Yayınları.
43. Kaya, R. (2001). Basından medyaya geçiş ve kavram olarak kamusal çıkar. *Karizma Dergisi*, (5), Medya Sayısı.
44. Keleş, Ç. (2012). *Finansal krizlerde IMF politikalarının rolü ve IMF'de reform hareketleri* [Yüksek lisans tezi], Bilecik Üniversitesi.
45. Kelsen, H., & Jestaedt, M. (2007). *Veröffentliche Schriften 1905–1910 und Selbstzeugnisse*. Mohr Siebeck Verlag.
46. Kızılkın, Z. (1988). Düşünce özgürlüğü ve kütüphanecilik. *Türk Kütüphaneciliği*, 2(4), 159–165.
47. Kütləvi İnformasiya Vasitələri Haqqında Azərbaycan Respublikasının Qanunu. (1999). <https://e-qanun.az/framework/7512>
48. Laçiner, M. S. (2015). *Türkiye'de medya ve politik klientalizm* [Doktora tezi]. İstanbul Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
49. Lijphart, A. (1989). *Çağdaş demokrasiler: Yirmi bir ülkede çoğunlukçu ve oydaşmacı yönetim örnekləri* (E. Özbudun & E. Onulduran, Çev.). Türk Demokrasi Vakfı ve Siyasi İlimler Derneği Ortak Yayını.
50. Mankan, V. (2020). Demokrasinin tarihsel evrimi. *Artuklu Kaime Uluslararası İktisadi ve İdari Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 3(2), 124.
51. McQuail, D. (1994). *Mass communication theory*. Sage Publications.
52. Media haqqında Azərbaycan Respublikasının Qanunu. (2021). <https://e-qanun.az/framework/49124>
53. Mehmet Emin, A. (2012). İfade özgürlüğünün tarihsel süreci ve milli güvenlik gerekçesiyle ifade özgürlüğünün kısıtlanması. *Ankara Üniversitesi Hukuk Fakültesi Dergisi (AUHFD)*, 61(1), 1–42.
54. Memmedov, N. (2007). Azərbaycan'da telekomünikasyon ortamının seviyesi nasıldır? *TV Plyus Dergisi*, (1).
55. Bakı Xəbər. (2012). Mətbuat Şurasının 9 illik yolu... https://www.anl.az/down/meqale/baki_xeber/2012/mart/239607.htm
56. Mill, J. S. (2012). *Hürriyyət üstünə* (M. O. Dostel, Çev.). Liberte Yayınları.
57. Miller, D., Coleman, J., Connoly, W., & Ryan, A. (1994). *Blackwell'in siyasal düşünce ansiklopedisi* (B. Peker & N. Kırac, Çev.). Ümit Yayıncılık.
58. Mirakif, A. (2024). Azərbaycan'da jurnalistika fakültəsinə ehtiyac varmı? – Açıqlama. <https://konkret.az/azerbaycanda-jurnalistika-fakultesine-ehciyac-varmi-aciqlama/>
59. Özgen, M. (1998). *Kurumsal, kuramsal ve tarihsel açıdan gazetecinin etik kimliği*. Gazeteciler Cemiyeti.
60. Nuriyev, A. (2021). Jurnalistika-ixtisas seçimi və şərtləri. <https://ixtisas.az/az/blog/jurnalistika-ixtisas-secimi-ve-sertler-132>
61. Orucov, A. (2006). *Azərbaycan dilinin açıqlayıcı sözlüyü* (Cilt 2). Doğu-Batı.
62. Özbudun, E. (1975). *Türkiye'de sosyal değişme ve siyasal katılma*. Ankara Üniversitesi Hukuk Fakültesi Yayınları.
63. Pirizade, N. (2019). *On dokuzuncu yüzyıldan günümüze Azərbaycan basını: Öncüller, ardıllar ve önemli dönüm noktaları* [Yüksek lisans tezi]. Atatürk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
64. Qocayev, İ. (2017). İxtisaslı və ixtisassız jurnalistlər... <https://sherg.az/arxiv/35136>
65. Quliyev, Ə. (2020, Temmuz 14). XX əsrin ilk anadilli qəzeti – “Şərqi-Rus”. *Xalq qəzeti*, s. 9. <https://www.anl.az/down/meqale/xalqqazeti/2020/iyul/716142.htm>
66. Reporters Without Borders (RSF). (2021). *Azerbaijan 2021*. https://rsf.org/en/analyse_region-ale/489
67. Reporters Without Borders (RSF). (2023). *Azerbaijan 2023*. https://rsf.org/en/analyse_region-ale/1004
68. Reporters Without Borders (RSF). (2024). *Azerbaijan 2024*. <https://rsf.org/en/country/azerbaijan>
69. Rütəmov, A. (2011). *Jurnalistikanın əsasları (Jurnalistikaya giriş)*. AzTU Nəşriyyatı.
70. Salamov, N. (2020, Ekim 21–23). *Azərbaycan'da yeni medya eğitimi: Tarihsel gelişim, teorik çalışmalar ve pratikteki yansımaları*. Üsküdar Üniversitesi İletişim Fakültesi 7. Uluslararası İletişim Günleri “Dijital Çağda İletişim Eğitimi” Sempozyumu.
71. Sartori, G. (1993). *Demokrasi teorisine geri dönüş* (T. Karamustafaoğlu & M. Turhan, Çev.). Türk Demokrasi Vakfı Yayınları.
72. Schmidt, A. G. (2002). *Demokrasi kuramlarına giriş* (M. E. Köktaş, Çev., 2. Baskı). Vadi Yayınları.
73. Selimov, H. (1999). AHC daha kendi geleceyi karşısındadır. *Azadlık Gazetesi*, 31, 8.
74. Tartanoğlu, A. (1994). *Baskın basın'ın mı? ÇGD Yayınları*.
75. Temir, E. (2021). *30. yılında Türk cumhuriyetleri ulusal politika* (F. Yaldız, Ed.). Nobel Akademik Yayıncılık.
76. Touraine, A. (2011). *Demokrasi nedir* (O. Kunal, Çev.). Yapı Kredi Yayınları.
77. TÜGİK. (1997). *Türkiye'de düşünce özgürlüğü* (Hazırlayan: İ. Ö. Kaboğlu). Türkiye Genç İşadamları Derneği Yüksek Kurulu.
78. Türkmen, T. (2011). *Demokratik toplumun oluşumunda medyanın rolü* [Yüksek lisans tezi]. Atatürk Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
79. Werhan, K. (2004). *Freedom of speech: A reference guide to the United States Constitution*. Praeger Publishers.
80. Xalidoğlu, S. (2016). Ənənəvi mediadan internet mediaya doğru: Problemlər, çağırışlar. In Ş. Vəliyev (Ed.), *Elm və Təhsil Nəşriyyatı*, 23–38. Bakı.

81. Yakışır, Y. (2009). *Medya ve demokrasi ilişkisi: Medyanın demokratik rolünü yeniden düşünmek* [Yüksek lisans tezi]. Kocaeli Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.

82. Yaqublu, N. (1999). *Azərbaycan milli istiqlal mübarizəsi və Məmməd Əmin Rəsulzadə*. Bakı.

83. Yazıcı, F. (2008). İfade özgürlüğü ve Avrupa Birliği medya politikasına uyum çerçevesinde televizyon programlarının sınıflandırılması sorunu [Yüksek

lisans tezi]. Gazi Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.

84. Yılmaz, Y. (2011). *Siyasal sistem ve medya kuramları bağlamında Türkiye’de gazeteciliğin mesleki kimlik sorunu ve bir alan araştırması* [Doktora tezi]. Marmara Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.

85. Yüksel, Ö. (2017). *Seçme seçilme hakkı ve insan hakları* [Yüksek lisans tezi]. Maltepe Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.